

The role of crowd-mapping and PGIS in post-emergency humanitarian operations

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Considering that the so-called “digital humanitarianism” can support climate justice by providing tools and platforms for data collection, analysis, and dissemination that empower vulnerable communities to advocate for their rights and mobilize for climate action and advance equitable solutions, we could subscribe it can amplify the voices of marginalized communities, enhance transparency and accountability, and promote greater inclusivity in the fight for climate justice. Authors in [1] state the general opinion that among practitioners, researchers, and activists, the practice of Web-GIS with OSM is more advanced than the underlying theory of its applications. Digital humanitarianism is located at the intersection of new socio-technical practices, a new epistemology, and new institutional relationships [2,3].

Overall, within the context of digital humanitarianism, as demonstrated by web-map services and communities like Ushahidi or the Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team (HOT), traditional humanitarian organizations delegate tasks connected to the collection, production, processing, dissemination, and mapping of humanitarian data to a vast, participatory network of non-specialist volunteers.

People, giving examples of the huge scale of Volunteer Geographic Information (VGI), contribute to OpenStreetMap [4] and publish their maps, which has proven particularly beneficial in remote regions that Google has not yet covered and which experienced catastrophic events related to natural disasters.

When PGIS (Participatory GIS) maps reflect perceptions of the world (or parts of it), the “qualitative” aspect of GIS is enriched by data gathered through methods like ethnographic interviews, focus groups, and participatory observations [5].

The study aims to precisely examine how crowd-mapping and PGIS could turn out to be a crucial tool in contributing to humanitarian projects by analyzing the specific characteristics and outcomes of the selected application case, identifying the mechanisms through which geospatial data - documented through observations and crowd-sourced data - play a role in shaping participatory processes [6]. By integrating geodata collected and validated by community members into the planning framework, it could be further explored, within the broader research in which this study is integrated, how this participatory approach enhances the accuracy of data, reflects local knowledge, and empowers communities in decision-making. The study fosters collaboration between stakeholders by ensuring that

participatory planning outcomes are more inclusive and responsive to local needs, the criticalities and problems that emerged, and the possible strategies to be activated to tackle them especially in contexts where people living in rural and remote areas and in peri-urban areas face problems such as inadequate access to essential resources, and are more exposed to low quality basic services (health and education) and the effects of natural disasters.

The current case study of planning a humanitarian mapping intervention in a post-emergency context (Morocco 2023) is part of a PhD research project at the University of Palermo's CSTE, with the scientific expertise in Social Lab of researchers from the University of Catania's DISFOR (Department of Educational Sciences) in Italy. The fieldwork is part of an emergency intervention led by a five NGOs consortium project financed by Caritas, where the humanitarian mapping activities were coordinated by COPEOfficinaSociale (Social Research Center of the NGO CO.P.E. Cooperazione Paesi Emergenti) with an overall objective of assisting the population impacted by the earthquake that struck in Morocco on September 8 and 9, 2023. As part of this intervention, which calls for various support measures (distribution of family kits, distribution of housing tents and school modules, social-health interventions and psychological support), a humanitarian mapping action, indeed, has been carried out in collaboration with El Amane Association of Marrakech and the young women of a social radio station called "Radio El Amane" attentive to 'open data'. The project starts from an integrated strategy that brings together humanitarian mapping and "future labs", presenting a dynamic approach to addressing social challenges in post-emergency contexts and crisis areas.

The project was implemented based on 3 strategic milestones: Share of experiences and knowledge on mapping activities and their application in the humanitarian context of reference (phases 1 and 2); geo-data elaboration for disaster risk reduction and response (phases 2 and 3); contribute to the OSM community and develop a project outcome using a story-map tool (phase 3), still in progress.

The project's phases include six components:

1. HOT project (Phase 1) - the team actively participated in the HOT project by mapping different polygons/buildings delimiting territorial areas hit by the earthquake, as a part of an initiative by the Open Mapping Hub for West and Northern Africa. It has engaged a diverse group of contributors across five distinct initiatives, resulting in the collection of a significant amount of data: it shows significant progress toward project completion with 62,535 changesets created by 10,235 contributors (data last consulted June 2024).

2. Mapathon (Phase 2) - the mapping group, consisting of four women (Chaimaa Aaglli, Manar Abissate, Aya Elhourri, Nadia Elmejjati, and the Mapping Coordinator Halima Oulami, President of El Amane Association and researcher at LERMA) and one man (Miloud Ouchala, Professor from University of Marrakech, LERMA), actively participated with three representatives in the mapathon activity held in January 2023. The Emerging Business Factory (EBF) and the Global Diversity Foundation (GDF) worked together to monitor and assess humanitarian efforts following earthquakes in the High Atlas region through the Mapathons website, which uses the Tasking Manager. The mapathon aimed to consolidate data and information on earthquake response via the Mapathons website, utilising established methodologies and prior expertise. Local, national, and international organizations were invited to support EBF's initiative to create an accessible and secure platform for earthquake response activities, providing data, information, and maps.

3. PGIS / Field visits - With concern to the field visit missions in the province of El Haouz and Chichaoua the established mapping team used the following tools and methods: Google Earth Pro for printing maps and involving local residents in their distribution / OsmAnd and Mapillary (Android for digital recording on smartphone devices) / Google Earth Pro and ArcMap for comprehensive mapping / Web-GIS platforms like OSM or Missing Maps, HOT Tasking Manager for data collection / Google Earth Pro, for printing for the focus groups with the community.

The integration with ArcMap was a key methodology adopted to improve location accuracy in OsmAnd. The primary aim of this integration was to overlay the mapped data obtained with their surveys onto existing digital maps. The process began with scanning the printed maps from Google Earth Pro. The mapping team then used ArcMap to merge these scanned maps with the digital maps available in the software. This step allowed them to achieve an integrated representation of the mapped information. Once merged, they integrated the field data into Excel spreadsheets. This allowed them to organize and manipulate the data more effectively, preparing it for seamless integration with digital maps. Subsequently, they converted the data from ArcMap's SHP format to OsmAnd's GPX format. This conversion was crucial to ensure a smooth and uninterrupted data transition between the two systems, enabling seamless integration. Finally, to ensure precise geolocation of points of interest in the douars, considering both territorial landmarks and WEF (Water, Energy, Food) factors, mappers used OsmAnd to automatically geolocate entities based on converted data. This included 1) territorial features such as water sources, wells, and earthquake-damaged roads, and 2) anthropic features like places of worship, schools, small shops, solar energy installations, crops, cooperatives, and interests in forming associations. This approach provided additional assurance of the precision and reliability of the mapped information. The humanitarian mapping process was conducted using participatory methodologies, actively involving local communities in the data collection and analysis. This inclusive approach ensured the representativeness of the collected information and fostered greater engagement from the directly affected individuals. The data collected in the initial mapped douars have been presented in a shared geoportal elaborated with ArcGIS (<https://www.arcgis.com/apps/instant/portfolio/index.html?appid=ddf0601c4eb84adba9dde6a78ac6d6fc>).

4. Future Lab (Phase 2) - On March 24, under the coordination of Professor Augusto Gamuzza from University of Catania (DISFOR), five "future labs", a collaborative initiative designed to address and innovate solutions for challenges, were held in five different douars within the Commune of Assif El Mal (Imi Oussif, Ait Abaid, Tabonout, Tafroukht, Tloutimte). The future labs' working groups were composed of territorial representatives and stakeholders from diverse sectors like volunteers, community leaders, and local organization members (e.g., muqaddim, kaid, school teachers, association representatives). Furthermore, the groups were organized by gender to address specific gender-related needs effectively.

5. OpenStreetMap (Phase 3) - The next step will be to upload the data to OpenStreetMap, which will allow the collected information to be shared with the community and made accessible to a wider audience.

6. Story Map (Phase 3) - The final step will develop a project outcome using a story-map tool, partially developed by the Geo-portal already realized.

This activity provided a thorough understanding of the needs and challenges faced by earthquake-affected communities, using data to guide effective assistance and

reconstruction efforts. For the first time in Morocco's remote areas, the mapping of settlements, land use, and disaster risk zones was accomplished with local knowledge. Various tools and methods were employed for spatial learning and advocacy, including satellite imagery, GPS surveys, participatory mapping, OSM data and HOT initiatives, GIS analysis, complemented by interviews and field surveys (future labs). The integration of Indigenous Geographic Knowledge (IGK) supports peer-to-peer engagement and could turn out to be an important source of information for authorities and policy planners about community concerns. The case study highlights the importance of including diverse geographical perspectives, particularly from women. In the context of Africa, the digital divide is particularly pronounced, with significant progress in digital mapping and other technological advancements being made in industrialized countries, while the field remains largely underexplored in remote areas of the African continent. The fact that the case study was developed in a vulnerable context of North Africa is meant to emphasize the need to address this imbalance.

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